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METHODS OF TEACHING LISTENING COMPREHENSION IN ESP CLASSES

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Annotation: *One of the methodological standards of coaching a overseas language is the precept of integration, which implies, amongst different things, the simultaneous improvement of communicative, professionally communicative, informational, educational and social abilities, as nicely as the impossibility in the manner of coaching a selected sort of speech hobby or component of the language, to exclude different kinds speech hobby and factors of language.*

Keywords: *broaden, intellectual, techniques, together memory, wondering therefore, speech, observe, excessive, significance*

This method that once coaching a overseas language for unique functions, not one of the styles of speech hobby ought to be excluded from the academic manner. In different words, even as coaching listening, we concurrently train effective styles of speech hobby, shape the cognitive hobby of college students and broaden intellectual techniques together with memory, wondering and , therefore, speech. We observe the excessive significance of the implementation of the above precept for coaching a overseas language for expert functions. However, today, the formation by a overseas language of the cappotential to assume logically, examine and spotlight the principle thing, evaluate and contrast, i. e. the abilities which can be essential for the destiny educational and expert sports of modern college students are hampered via way of many factors. Among them, there's an inadequate variety of lecture room instructions in English, which contradicts the excessive necessities for graduates of technical universities. THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS It is feasible to solve this contradiction via way of the use of e-getting to know equipment withinside the academic manner. The simplest e-getting to know implementation version is the mixed getting to know version. The use of a version of mixed getting to know of a overseas language for unique functions with a predominance of impartial paintings in an engineering and technical college obliges instructors to broaden assets in an effort to enhance the mastery of diverse styles of speech hobby and factors of the language. In the formation of professionally orientated communicative competence of college students of a technical college, a clean predominance is historically feature of analyzing - a receptive kind of speech hobby that permits you to get new statistics maximum efficiently. However, it ought to be diagnosed that listening performs an similarly critical function in overseas language communication. "Note that in the manner of coaching ESP, with the dominant of analyzing because the maximum available manner of acquiring professionally good sized statistics, different kinds of speech hobby ought to be diagnosed as similarly critical, which, undoubtedly, ought to be pondered in the device of physical activities of the route": listening 45% of the time, talking - 30%, analyzing - 16%, writing - 9%". Therefore, we consider that in their destiny expert sports, whilst attempting to find statistics, graduates of technical universities will ought to deal now no longer best with published

substances, however additionally with audio and video assets. In addition, many problems are clarified within the route of debate with colleagues and employees, M. G. Shamsitdinova; Ind J Human Soc Sci; Vol-2, Iss-11 (Nov, 2021): 75-79 Corresponding Author: Manzura Gapporovna Shamsitdinova seventy six which calls for the formation of the abilities of paying attention to statistics, its operational evaluation and separating the principle and the secondary. Consequently, the powerful company of listening schooling for expert functions is an critical mission going through instructors at the gift stage. Listening is described as a receptive kind of speech hobby (TSA), which is the simultaneous notion and knowledge of speech via way of ear. It ought to be mentioned that that is one of the maximum tough for gaining knowledge of the TSA, for the reason that it is an lively manner, throughout which the extreme paintings of all intellectual and intellectual mechanisms occurs, the acquired statistics is perceived in the shape of a sound shape, its processing, reputation and knowledge of the meaning. The purpose of coaching listening at a technical college is to shape techniques for the notion and knowledge of statistics via way of ear (extracting statistics from a sounding text) with the following use of the statistics acquired in a overseas language oral or written communication. In different words, the scholar should learn how to extract the statistics he desires now no longer best from a published source, however additionally from audio or video assets a good way to use those substances in in addition paintings to examine, systematize, evaluate, select the principle thing, etc. By listening techniques, we suggest a set of moves aimed at reaching a purpose, namely, knowledge sounding speech in the framework of professionally

Aim of coaching while the subject matter is acquainted to college students from theoretical courses. In this case, they are able to recognition on the shape of expression, obtain a whole expertise of the content material of the textual content and memorize linguistic forms. On the opposite hand, such listening can serve as a supply of extra theoretical facts while making ready Besides YOU TUBE resources, there are many, essays, reports, etc. Different reassets of proper texts. Their benefit is the truth that they are created now no longer for instructional purposes (coaching overseas language listening), however for experts within the expert the field. Content material of listening schooling relies upon often on the desires and degree of schooling, inside the bounds of which a sure stage of auditory talents and skills is formed, as nicely as on the unique getting to know conditions. First, the choice of schooling content material ought to meet the standards of necessity and sufficiency to obtain the meant desires in coaching listening. Secondly, while deciding on the content material of schooling, the precept of the provision of its assimilation ought to be implemented, that is, the choice of the content material of schooling ought to be made taking into account the college students' cappotential to assimilate the decided on instructional material, taking into consideration their actual stage of language proficiency. When growing a block of obligations for the formation of listening talents and developing tips for college kids to finish those obligations (Listening guide / strategies), the following parameters ought to Psychophysical mechanisms be taken into account: concerned in the implementation of a specific form of Tolisting; he real form of listening. The latter require greater exact attention because of their significance in organizing paintings Guided Listening on listening. Instructional listening, acts as a coaching tool, also can act as a manner of introducing language material, shape a prerequisite for the formation of oral speech talents, the formation and development of communicative listening talents. Repeated listening at some point of extracurricular unbiased paintings and two times at some point of joint lecture room paintings with the trainer permits you to obtain a greater whole expertise of audio or video material, its memorization and in addition interpretation of its content material and

Linguistic shape, specifically within the case while the listened textual content is used to shape the talents Communicative Listening, as of oral or written communication. Antagonistic to instructional listening, is aimed at comprehending and comprehending spoken speech via way of means of being attentive to it once. Depending at the communicative attitude, the subsequent Skim listening - listening with an subtypes of listening are distinguished: expertise of the primary content material or introductory listening, the reason of which is to technique the semantic facts of the sounding textual content, separate the brand new from the known, spotlight and repair the maximum critical facts in reminiscence. Study assignments aimed at this kind of listening and growing the important talents consist of Predicting the: content material of the textual content via way of means of the identify earlier than listening, (Read the identify of the textual content you will hear.

USED LITERATURE:

1. O'MALLEY, J. M., Chamot, A. U., & Küpper, L. (1989). Listening comprehension strategies in second language acquisition. *Applied linguistics*, 10(4), 418-437.
2. Paribakht, T. S., & Wesche, M. B. (1993). Reading comprehension and second language development in a comprehension-based ESL program. *TESL Canada journal*, 09-29.
3. Rubin, J. (1994). A review of second language listening comprehension research. *The modern language journal*, 78(2), 199-221.
4. Ruhe, V. (1996). Graphics and listening comprehension. *TESL Canada Journal*, 45-60.
5. Salakhova, E. Z., & Shamsitdinova, M. G. (2020). **ADVANCED PEDOGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN EDUCATION IN THE 21- ST CENTURY**. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (5), 743-746